

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1915	Alan Lomax	1934		1996		American ethnomusicologist, best known for his numerous field recordings of folk music of the 20th century	1915-2002
1915	Dhimitër Shuteriqi	1935		2003		Albanian scholar (literature, history, and folklore), literary historian, and writer	1915-2003
1915	Maria Corti	1936	1936	1991	w	Italian philologist, literary critic, and novelist	1915-2002
1915	Henry M. Hoenigswald	1936	1936	1985		German-American linguist	1915-2003
1915	Lawrence Kaelter Rosinger	1937	No	1991		American specialist on modern East Asia, focusing on China and India	1915-1994
1915	Jean Bassett Johnson	1938	No	1942		American anthropologist and linguist	1915-2005
1915	Armas Salonen	1938	1950	1978		Finnish Assyriologist	1915-1981
1915	Álvaro d'Ors	1939	1941	1985		Spanish jurist and classical philologist	1915-2004
1915	Chaim Menachem Rabin	1939	1939	1985		German-British-Israeli professor of Hebrew and Semitic languages	1915-1996
1915	Abraham Sachs	1939	1939	1983		American assyriologist	1915-1983
1915	Joseph Greenberg	1940	1940	1985		American linguist (linguistic typology and the genetic classification of languages)	1915-2001
1915	Yehoshua Bar-Hillel	1940	1945	1975		Israeli philosopher, mathematician, and linguist (machine translation and formal linguistics)	1915-1975
1915	Isabel Crook	1940	No	1985	w	Canadian anthropologist and former professor at Beijing Foreign Studies University	1915-2023
1915	Kurt Aland	1941	1941	1983		German theologian and biblical scholar who specialized in New Testament textual criticism	1915-1994
1915	Gaëtan Picon	1945		1976		French author: essayist, art and literature critic, and art and literature historian	1915-1976
1915	Ernst Pulgram	1946	1946	1986		Austrian-American linguist	1915-2005
1915	James Robert Hightower	1946	1946	1981		American sinologist	1915-2006
1915	William J. Gedney	1947	1947	1980		American linguist (Southeast Asian language, Tai historical linguistics)	1915-1999
1915	Elman Service	1947	1951	1985		American cultural anthropologist (theorist of cultural evolution and formulator of the nomenclature now in standard use to categorize primitive societies as bands, tribes, chiefdoms, and states)	1915-1996

1915 Markus Barth	1947	1947	1985	Swiss scholar of theology	1915-1994
1915 Roland Barthes	1948	1948	1980	French literary theorist, philosopher, critic, and semiotician	1915-1980
1915 Rachel Bromwich	1948	1939	1976 w	British (Welsh) scholar (medieval Welsh literature, Celtic Languages and Literature)	1915-2010
1915 Robert Lado	1948		1980	American expert on modern linguistics	1915-1995
1915 James Thorpe	1948 No		1999	American director of the Huntington Library, and a professor of English	1915-2009
1915 Joseph B. Casagrande	1948	1951	1982	American anthropologist	1915-1982
1915 Igor M. Diakonoff	1949	1949	1975	Russian historian, linguist, and translator and a renowned expert on the Ancient Near East and its languages	1915-1999
1915 Lilian Hamilton Jeffery	1949		1986 w	British archaeologist, classical philologist and epigraphist	1915-1986
1915 Karl Hoffmann	1951	1951	1983	German linguist who specialized in Indo-European and Indo-Iranian studies	1915-1996
1915 Hans Conzelmann	1951	1951	1978	German Protestant, German theologian and New Testament scholar	1915-1989
1915 Mahir Domi	1954		2000	Albanian linguist	1915-2000
1915 Koldo Mitxelena	1955	1959	1987	Spanish (Basque) linguist	1915-1987
1916 Charles F. Hockett	1938	1939	1982	American linguist (American structuralist linguistics) and anthropologist	1916-2000
1916 Winfred P. Lehmann	1938	1938	1986	American linguist (historical linguistics, Proto-Indo-European and Proto-Germanic), machine translation	1916-2007
1916 Benjamin I. Schwartz	1938	1938	1987	American academic, political scientist, and sinologist (topics in Chinese politics and intellectual history)	1916-1999
1916 Johannes Gijbertus de Casparis	1940		1986	Dutch orientalist and indologist	1916-2002
1916 Tine Logar	1941	1941	1978	Slovenian historical linguist, dialectologist, and university professor	1916-2002
1916 Ivan Venedikov	1942 No		1997	Bulgarian archaeologist, historian, thracologist and philologist	1916-1997
1916 Brian Ó Cuív	1942 No		1988	Irish Celtic scholar who specialised in Irish history and philology	1916-1999

1916	Hans Fränkel	1942	1942	1987	German-American sinologist (Chinese poetry and literature)	1916-2003
1916	M. N. Srinivas	1942	1952	1979 w	Indian sociologist and social anthropologist	1916-1999
1916	Oreste Pucciani	1943	1943	1979	American pioneer teacher of Jean-Paul Sartre's philosophy at UCLA	1916-1999
1916	Carlo Tullio Altan	1943		1987	Italian anthropologist, sociologist and philosopher	1916-2005
1916	John Victor Murra	1943	1956	1982	Ukrainian-American professor of anthropology and a researcher of the Inca Empire	1916-2006
1916	Wilfred Cantwell Smith	1943	1948	1984	Canadian Islamicist, comparative religion scholar, and Presbyterian minister	1916-2000
1916	Rudolf Vleeskruijer	1947	1951	1966	Dutch professor in the English language and Old English literature	1916-1966
1916	Lanfranco Ricci	1947		2008	Italian Ethiopianist	1916-2007
1916	John Mann Goggin	1947	1948	1963	American cultural anthropologist in the southwest, southeast, Mexico, and Caribbean, primarily focusing on the ethnology, cultural history, and typology of artifacts from archaeological sites	1916-1963
1916	John Milton Roberts	1947	1947	1987	American anthropologist who developed the field of expressive culture in a series of studies on games in culture, and published over 50 articles on these subjects	1916-1990
1916	Dario Cabanelas	1948	1948	1985	Spanish one of the most important Spanish Arabists of the 20th century	1916-1992
1916	Daniel H. H. Ingalls Sr.	1949	1949	1983	American the Wales Professor of Sanskrit	1916-1999
1916	Eleanor Hadley	1949		1984 w	American academic, economist, and professor at Smith College (Japanologist)	1916-2007
1916	E. L. Peters	1951	1951	1984	British social anthropologist	1916-1987
1916	Ronald Berndt	1951	1955	1981	Australian social anthropologist	1916-1990
1916	Eduardo Dozier	1952	1952	1971	American (Tewi-Pueblo Native) anthropologist and linguist	1916-1971
1916	Edward Pasqual Dozier	1952	1952	1971	American-Pueblo Native anthropologist and linguist	1916-1971
1916	Sebastian Shaumyan	1952	1962	1986	Armenian American theoretician of linguistics and an outspoken adherent of structuralist analysis	1916-2007
1916	Tomás de Bhaldraithe	1954	No	1986	Irish language scholar and lexicographer	1916-1996
1916	D. C. H. Rieu	1957		1980	British classical scholar	1916-2008
1916	Jean-Michel Thierry	1957		1989	French physician and art historian	1916-2011

1916	Andrey Korsakov	1958	1958	2000	Ukrainian American linguist and language philosopher (grammar of the English language and father of Grammar School in Ukraine)	1916-2007
1917	Velta Ruke-Dravina	1939	1959	1984 w	Latvian-Swedish linguist and folklorist	1917-2003
1917	Donald Herbert	1939	1949	1996	American linguistic philosopher (philosophy of mind, philosophy of language, and action theory)	1917-2003
1917	Giorgio Colli	1939	1939	1979	Italian philosopher, philologist and historian	1917-1979
1917	Bhogilal Sandesara	1939	1950	1975	Indian literary critic, scholar and editor	1917-1995
1917	Jean Hani	1939		1976	French philosopher and Traditionalist author, and a professor of Greek civilization and literature	1917-2012
1917	Marian Plezia	1939	1939	1988	Polish classical philologist, medievalist, lexicographer	1917-1996
1917	Alvin Liberman	1940	1942	1998	American psychologist and linguist (psychological research in speech perception)	1917-2000
1917	János Harmatta	1940	1940	1986	Hungarian linguist	1917-2004
1917	Elizabeth Colson	1943	1945	1998 w	American social anthropologist and professor emerita of anthropology	1917-2016
1917	Mabel Lang	1943	1943	1991 w	American archaeologist and scholar of Classical Greek and Mycenaean culture	1917-2010
1917	Elizabeth Marie Pope	1944	1944	1982 w	American author and educator specializing in Elizabethan England and the works of John Milton and William Shakespeare	1917-1992
1917	G. Johannes Botterweck	1944	1944	1981	German theologian, Old Testament scholar and dean of the Catholic Theological Faculty	1917-1981
1917	Peter Runham Ackroyd	1945	1945	1990	British Biblical scholar, Anglican priest, and former Congregational minister	1917-2005
1917	Martin Alexander Kloster-Jensen	1946	1961	1995	Norwegian professor of phonetics and communication	1917-2011
1917	Henry Allan Gleason	1946	1946	1982	American linguist	1917-2007
1917	Idriz Ajeti	1947	1958	2003	Albanian Linguist, Albanologist	1917-2019
1917	Walter Harding	1947	1950	1983	American distinguished professor of English	1917-1996
1917	Paul Gebhard	1947	1947	1986	American anthropologist and sexologist	1917-2015
1917	Raymond Picard	1947	1956	1975	French author, prominent Sorbonne professor and Jean Racine scholar	1917-1975
1917	D. R. Shackleton Bailey	1948		1988	British scholar of Latin literature (particularly in the field of textual criticism)	1917-2005

1917 Algirdas Julien Greimas	1949	1949	1990	Lithuanian literary scientist (Semiotics, structural linguistics)	1917-1992
1917 Pentti Aalto	1949	1949	1980	Finnish linguist	1917-1998
1917 Annette Laming-Emperaire	1949		1977 w	French archeologist	1917-1977
1917 Helen Codere	1950	1950	1982 w	American cultural anthropologist	1917-2009
1917 Sarup Singh	1953	1953	1974	Indian academic turned politician (literary scientist)	1917-2003
1917 Irène Mélikoff	1954	1957	1989 w	Azerbaijani-French Turkologist	1917-2009
1917 Jolán Babus	1954 No		1967 w	Hungarian ethnographer and teacher	1917-1967
1917 Musa Haji Ismail Galal	1955		1970	Somali writer, scholar, linguist, historian and polymath	1917-1980
1917 William Clifford Massey	1955	1955	1974	American anthropologist who played a key role in the study of the prehistory of the Baja California Peninsula in Mexico	1917-1974
1917 Milada Blekastad	1958	1969	1987 w	Norwegian literary histories, turnovers, cultural worker	1917-2003
1917 Fereydoun Motamed	1962		1979	Iranian linguist	1917-1993
1918 John Howland Rowe	1940	1947	1988	American archaeologist and anthropologist known for his extensive research on Peru, especially on the Inca civilization	1918-2004
1918 David H. French	1943	1949	1988	American anthropologist and linguist	1918-1994
1918 Alain Guy	1943	1943	1987	French philologist and hispanist	1918-1998
1918 László Mezey	1944	1944	1984	Hungarian medievalist and palaeographer	1918-1984
1918 Stefan Strelcyn	1945		1981	Polish scholar of Ethiopian Studies and a Semitist	1918-1981
1918 Rita Schober	1945	1945	1978	German scholar of Romance studies and literature	1918-2012
1918 Yeleazar Meletinsky	1945	1945	1994	Ukrainian-Russian scholar famous for his seminal studies of folklore, literature, philology and the history and theory of narrative	1918-2005
1918 Catherine Berndt	1946	1955	1994 w	New Zealand-Australian anthropologist	1918-1994
1918 M. E. Grenander	1946	1948	1989 w	American professor of English and philanthropist	1918-1998
1918 Emmett L. Bennett Jr.	1947	1947	1988	American classicist and philologist (the ancient Minoan language known as Linear B)	1918-2011
1918 Jacqueline Pirenne	1947	1954	1990 w	French archaeologist and epigrapher	1918-1990
1918 David Aberle	1947	1950	1983	American anthropologist	1918-2004
1918 Emidio De Felice	1948		1981	Italian linguist and lexicographer	1918-1993
1918 John Arundel Barnes	1948	1951	1982	Australian and British social anthropologist	1918-2010
1918 Leigh Lisker	1949	1949	1989	American linguist and phonetician	1918-2006

1918 J. Clyde Mitchell	1949		1985	British sociologist and anthropologist	1918-1995
1918 David M. Schneider	1949	1949	1986	American cultural anthropologist, best known for his studies of kinship and as a major proponent of the symbolic anthropology approach to cultural anthropology	1918-1995
1918 W. Sidney Allen	1949		1982	British linguist and philologist, best known for his work on Indo-European phonology	1918-2004
1918 Joseph Frank	1950	1952	1985	American literary scholar and leading expert on the life and work of Russian novelist Fyodor Dostoevsky	1918-2013
1918 Robert Escarpit	1950		1983	French academic, writer and journalist	1918-2000
1918 Donald Wiseman	1950		1982	British biblical scholar, archaeologist and Assyriologist	1918-2010
1918 Joyce Reynolds	1950	No	not retired w	British classicist and academic, specialising in Roman historical epigraphy	1924-2019
1918 Arne-Johan Henrichsen	1951	1951	1977	Norwegian philologist	1918-2005
1918 Ray Birdwhistell	1951	1951	1988	American anthropologist who founded kinesics as a field of inquiry and research	1918-1994
1918 Roch Valin	1952		1986	Canadian linguist and Romanist	1918-2012
1918 Sheila Patterson	1953	No	1987 w	British social anthropologist who specialised in race, immigration, and race and ethnic relations	1918-1998
1918 Thelma D. Sullivan	1963	1968	1981	American paleographer, linguist and translator, regarded as one of the foremost scholars in the 20th century of the Classical Nahuatl language	1918-1981
1918 Florence Connolly Shipek	1965	1977	1983 w	American Native anthropologist and ethnohistorian, a leading authority on Southern California Indians	1918-2003
1919 César Graña	1939	1957	1986	Peruvian sociologist and anthropologist	1919-1986
1919 Hasan Eren	1941	1942	1993	Turkish academic etymologist, linguist, Turkologist, and Hungarologist	1919-2007
1919 Dorothy Jean Ray	1941	No	1985 w	American author and anthropologist best known for her study of Native Alaskan art and culture	1919-2007
1919 Helene J. Kantor	1944	1945	1978 w	American Near Eastern Archeologist and Art Historian in the Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations	1919-1993
1919 John Hurt Fisher	1945	1945	1986	American literary scholar, English professor, and medievalist	1919-2015
1919 Jafar Shahidi	1945		1991	Iranian distinguished scholar of the Persian language and literature and a renowned historian of Islam	1919-2008

1919 Julian Pitt-Rivers	1945	1953	1986	British social anthropologist, an ethnographer, and a professor at universities in three countries	1919-2001
1919 Kurt Baldinger	1946	1948	1984	Swiss linguist and philologist	1919-2007
1919 William Stokoe	1946	1946	1984	American linguist (American Sign Language, cheroology)	1919-2000
1919 Finn Hødnebo	1948	1948	1985	Norwegian philologist and a lexicographer	1919-2007
1919 Kåre Langvik-Johannessen	1948	1948	1989	Norwegian philologist, literary historian and translator	1919-2014
1919 Frank Kermode	1948		1982	British literary critic	1919-2010
1919 Wm Theodore de Bary	1948	1953	1989	American Sinologist and East Asian literary scholar, professor and administrator at Columbia University	1919-2017
1919 Omeljan Pritsak	1948	1948	1999	Ukrainian the first Mykhailo Hrushevsky Professor of Ukrainian History at Harvard University and the founder and first director (1973–1989) of the Harvard Ukrainian Research Institute	1919-2006
1919 Rudolf Macúch	1948	1948	1993	Slovakian linguist	1919-1993
1919 Masud Husain Khan	1948	1948	1978	Indian linguist, the first Professor Emeritus in Social Sciences at Aligarh Muslim University	1919-2010
1919 Barbara E. Ward	1949	1949	1983 w	British social anthropologist and academic, who specialised in Chinese society	1919-1983
1919 Ward Hunt Goodenough II	1949	1949	1987	American anthropologist, who has made contributions to kinship studies, linguistic anthropology, cross-cultural studies, and cognitive anthropology	1919-2013
1919 William S. Laughlin	1949	1949	1999	American anthropologist who carried on research and wrote about aboriginal peoples in the Aleutians and Greenland	1919-2001
1919 William G. Beasley	1950	1950	1983	British academic, author, editor, translator and Japanologist	1919-2006
1919 Pierre-Roland Giot	1950		1986	French anthropologist, archaeologist and geologist	1919-2002
1919 Aert Hendrik Kuipers	1951	1951	1983	Dutch linguist and phonetician	1919-2012
1919 Frank W. Wadsworth	1951		1987	American Shakespearean scholar, author, and sportsman	1919-2012
1919 Joan Bastardas i Parera	1951	1953	1985	Spanish Catalan Latinist and Romance philologist	1919-2009
1919 Ursula Wertheim	1952	1957	1979 w	German literary scholar and university teacher	1919-2006
1919 Alvar Ellegård	1953	1953	1984	Swedish linguist and scholar	1919-2008

1919 Prasert na Nagara	1953		1998	Thai scholar, researcher in studies of ancient Thai inscriptions	1919-2019
1919 Lawrence Krader	1953	1954	1982	American socialist anthropologist and ethnologist	1919-1998
1919 Juhan Peegel	1954	1954	1993	Estonian journalist, linguist and writer	1919-2007
1919 John Goody	1954	1954	1987	British social anthropologist	1919-2015
1919 Nigel D. Oram	1954		1985	British-Australian public servant, academic, ethnologist and anthropologist specialising in the Pacific and New Guinea and was an acknowledged specialist in Papuan oral history	1919-2003
1919 Eva J. Engel	1954	1954	1987 w	German scholar of German studies and an important editor of the collected works of Moses Mendelssohn	1919-2013
1919 Harry Leonard Shorto	1955 No		1984	British philologist and linguist (Mon language and Mon-Khmer)	1919-1995
1919 Shakir Mustafa Salim	1955	1955	1977	Iraqi social anthropologist	1919-1985
1919 Helen H. Bacon	1955	1955	1989 w	American professor of classics at Barnard College	1919-2007
1919 Isaac Fanous	1958	1958	1979	Egyptian artist and scholar, who specialized in Coptic art and founded its contemporary school	1919-2007
1919 Pearl Primus	1959	1978	1978 w	Trinidadian-American dancer, choreographer and anthropologist	1919-1994
1919 Abbas Zaryab	1960	1960	1995	Iranian historian, translator, literature Professor and Iranologist	1919-1995
1919 Lain Singh Bangdel	1963		1982	Nepali foremost artist, novelist, and art historian	1919-2002